

Navigating the ethical landscape: A systematic review of challenges in AI adoption within the accounting profession

A.S.M. Sufian Pabel^a | Wahida Akther^a

^aDepartment of Business Administration, Leading University, Sylhet, Bangladesh.

Abstract The use of artificial intelligence (AI) into the accounting profession has resulted in a new era of increased efficiency and automation. However, its rapid adoption has raised substantial ethical difficulties, calling into question the profession's ethical principles. This paper focuses on determining the ethical problems that emerge because of the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in the accounting profession through a systematic literature review. Among the ethical problems, bias, transparency, security and privacy, employment issues, accountability, accessibility, discrimination, financial fraud, lack of ethical principles, trust, unethical decision-making, and objectivity are the most dominant. By focusing on critical ethical issues related to AI implementation in the accounting profession, this study suggests an ethical governance framework that can be adopted to minimize ethical risk. This work is significant because it systematically highlights the original ethical challenges presented by AI in accounting and proposes a governance framework, emphasizing theoretical advancements and practical implementation through collaboration, regulation, and ethical accountability.

Keywords: technology, governance, regulation, automation, integrity

1. Introduction

Digital technological innovations are altering the workflow of the accounting profession (Kruskopf et al., 2020). In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has been used in several fields. The introduction of AI in accounting fields helps in the automation of routine tasks and improves efficiency and effectiveness by helping in gathering and processing data and assisting in decision-making processes (Bakarich & O'Brien, 2021). As the frequency of AI use in the accounting profession increases, the volume of ethical risk also increases. Taking these ethical risks into consideration illustrates the importance of coping with the ethical concerns of AI in accounting practices (Pazarskis et al., 2022). Organizations that use new technologies can grasp new opportunities and be able to improve themselves continuously; as a result, it is vital to solidify the AI application process in the form of innovation and reform in the accounting industry (Luo et al., 2018). Most accountants argue that the ethics of AI are important and concern that authorities must be involved in creating ethical legislation related to AI use in accounting practices (Fülöp et al., 2023).

Ethics in the accounting profession has been discussed for years (Fatt, 1995), and ethical considerations need to be incorporated into the academic curriculum of accounting students (Armstrong, 1993; McPhail, 1999; Mayer et al., 2005; Cameron & O'Leary, 2015). A prediction about AI integration in the accounting field states that, within a very short period, AI will alter the overall accounting structure and processes (Neely & Cook, 2011). The prevalent views about accountants highlight the necessity of acting with integrity and ethics, which highlights the importance of ethics in the accounting field. Yoon (2020) noted that the rapid technological revolution in the accounting domain, exacerbated by the COVID-19 epidemic, requires thorough knowledge of their proper use, as well as the mitigation of related risks and dangers. According to (Holmes & Douglass, 2022), accounting practitioners, especially those at Big 4 firms, are optimistic about AI's influence on their profession, anticipate changes in accounting education, and emphasize data handling skills, highlighting the importance of adaptability in accounting programs. A systematic literature review conducted by Barišić (2022) revealed that, according to most recent studies, the use of AI in accounting and auditing operations makes different ethical principles difficult. However, ethical implications related to AI use in business practices call for improved governance to mitigate ethical risk (Ashok et al., 2022). AI provides significant solutions in accounting practices with advanced machine learning techniques and algorithms by automating accounting practices, enhancing data analysis, and improving the accuracy and timeliness of financial reporting; however, along with these breakthroughs, AI has created complicated ethical issues such as prejudice, privacy breaches, and accountability problems (Sreseli, 2023). In data-driven decisions, a risk for algorithmic bias still exists (Akter et al., 2021; Aquino, 2023). Considering the importance of ethics in the accounting profession, deeply scrutinizing the ethical aspects of AI implementation in accounting practices is suggested (Leitner-Hanetseder et al., 2021; Sreseli, 2023). Despite much discussion

about the benefits of AI in the accounting profession, there remains a significant gap in how ethical governance frameworks may handle these concerns.

This paper aims to address this gap by undertaking a thorough analysis of the current literature to identify the most important ethical barriers to AI adoption in accounting and offering a governance structure for reducing these risks. This study addresses the following research questions:

- What are the most critical ethical concerns about AI in accounting?
- How can a governance framework be created to address these ethical concerns?

By answering these questions, this study not only adds to the scholarly debate on AI ethics but also provides practical insights into how accounting professionals might responsibly utilize AI technology while adhering to ethical norms.

2. Literature Review

2.1. AI and ethics: What?

AI refers to artificial intelligence, which is the emulation of human intellects in computers that are programmed to understand, learn, and solve problems in the same way as people do. It includes a wide range of technologies and approaches that allow machines to execute activities that normally require human intellect, such as speech recognition, visual perception, language translation, and decision-making. Dobrev (2012) tried to formalize the definition of AI in this way: "AI will be such a program which in an arbitrary world will cope not worse than a human." More broadly, artificial intelligence (AI) has been defined as a machine's capacity to execute cognitive processes associated with human brains, such as perception, reasoning, understanding, communicating with surroundings, resolving problems, decision-making, and even displaying creativity (Rai et al., 2019). Artificial intelligence (AI) is a developed computer program that can work like a human (Saleh, 2019) and imitate different complex human activities (Sheikh et al., 2023), which is a constantly evolving technological event in which many sectors want to capitalize on to increase efficiency while lowering costs (Hassani et al., 2020).

The terms "ethics" and "ethical" originated from the Greek word "ethos," which originally referred to codes of conduct and application, particularly those of one group as opposed to another, and eventually evolved to signify disposition or character (Dewey & Tufts, 1906). Ethics involves evaluating the moral aspects of activities and entails differentiating between what is ethical, good, or right and what is unethical, immoral, awful, or wrong (Thiroux, 2008). Identifying the difference between right and wrong is essential for navigating ethics, but deciding "the right thing" is sometimes difficult, especially in professional quandaries that rarely have a straightforward yes or no conclusion (Krishnamurthy, 2011).

2.2. AI and accounting history

The scholarly work on the use of AI in the accounting profession can be traced more than 40 years ago during the 1980s (Stancheva-Todorova, 2018). The expert system began to generate assessment and potential projections, as well as explanations of the results and analysis in auditing tasks (Hansen & Messier, 1982). This statement can be considered true because research regarding the use of expert systems and decision support systems has been evident in the work of (Abdolmohammadi, 1987) There is a mixed perception of the use of AI in accounting fields. The impacts of AI in accounting have long been discussed by several authors. O'Leary and O'Keefe (1997) indicate that expert systems have a beneficial effect on productivity parameters such as user control, access to top management, flexibility in decision-making, and the capacity to solve a broader spectrum of challenges in auditing and tax systems. Approximately 20 years ago, the application of backpropagation algorithms to incorporate indispensable and quantitative analysis for financial performance forecasting was discovered (Lam, 2004). The use of data mining technologies in accounting and auditing (Karcher, 1996; Dull & Tegarden, 1999) and in other fields is evident in the different scholarly works. Since the introduction of processes in the accounting field in 2010 (van der Aalst et al., 2012), robotic process automation (RPA) has become a concerning situation; however, it is still seen as a means of increasing efficiency and effectiveness according to many scholars (Fernandez & Aman, 2018; Cooper et al., 2019; Kokina & Blanchette, 2019; Lacurezeanu et al., 2020). Moreover, natural language processing (NLP) is used to reconcile accounts with accounting professionals to reduce labor requirements (Chew & Robinson, 2012). Early studies also provide intensified evidence of the use of machine learning methods for detecting and accessing risk and fraud in financial disclosures (Song et al., 2014). Machine learning in accounting and assurance improves forecasting capacities for future events, assisting with tasks involving evaluating source documents and risk assessment while simultaneously increasing comprehension of the underappreciated inductive reasoning technique; however, concerns about potential bias and ethical implications in research and practice persist (Cho et al., 2020). According to Schatsky and Muraskin (2015) the emergence of blockchain technology offers a secure, transparent, and extremely resilient system for documenting digital transactions, with the potential to revolutionize industries such as finance and redefine procedures such as accounting and auditing. To date, such a network produces an indelible record of misconduct and allows important accounting constitutions to collaborate and exchange information as peers while avoiding the risk of one entity seizing possession of the ledger (Sheldon, 2018). The discussion of cloud computing in the accounting profession was an alarming topic after 2010, and the impact of cloud computing in the

accounting profession was stated by researchers in their scholarly works (Du & Cong, 2010). The overall method of cloud accounting infrastructure was discussed briefly by Khanom (2017) with its future implications. The utilization of artificial intelligence in partnership with the accounting industry to create software and apps that improve internal control frameworks and the quality of accounting information (Askary et al., 2018). Currently, more updated AI mechanisms, such as fuzzy logic, are being used for automated decision-making (Emetaram & Uchime, 2021).

2.3. Impact of AI in accounting

The perks of using AI demonstrate an unprecedented narrative in which smart automation, cognitive enhancement, and sophisticated analytics merge to reshape the core concepts of accounting and finance, establishing accountants as developers of an increasingly data-driven future. An analysis of 150 research papers indicates that AI has a positive effect on the process of financing and accounting (Berdiyeva et al., 2021). Global commercial organizations are moving toward continuous accounting and reporting as a result of rapid technical development and stakeholder demands (Smith, 2018). Some of the major impacts of AI in accounting practices include the following:

- **Automate tasks:** Artificial intelligence (AI) is positioned to simplify organizational operations soon by automating a major number of regular and repetitive daily, weekly, or annual chores. Furthermore, it will improve the organization's ability to make quick decisions, resulting in keen insights from the easy examination of massive amounts of data (Nayak & Sahoo, 2021).

- **Changed organizational culture:** Corporate culture, regulatory backing, perceived utility, and simplicity of use all have direct beneficial impacts on AI adoption, whereas perceived value and ease of use also have beneficial indirect effects on accounting revenue along with behavioral motivation (Wael et al., 2024). It may be helpful to reveal possible hurdles, differences in adoption rates, or unintended repercussions that might influence the context of the incorporation of AI in corporate contexts further.

- **Data-driven decision making:** Accounting data stored in the cloud and analyzed via cloud-assisted applications not only allows for the immediate accessibility of financial data but also speeds up management decision-making procedures (KPMG, 2012). The automated handling of routine tasks, astute data extraction abilities, advanced data analysis, intelligent expense management, simple integration, expansion, and notable efficiency related to time as well as cost savings are all inherent in AI-driven accounting programs (Khanam & Hossain, 2023). It not only shortens the decision-making process but also offers executives intelligent and data-driven knowledge, promoting improved comprehension and strategically important decision-making.

- **Standardized accounting procedure:** The use of artificial intelligence has demonstrated the ability to complete standardized accounting operations independently without the need for human intervention; at the same time, in tasks with nonstandardization or interpretative ambiguities, it mimics human decision-making by adopting from users' previous choice patterns (Özdoğan, 2017). The ramifications of artificial intelligence (AI), big data, blockchain technology (BT), corporate analytics, and XML-driven markup languages have been applied for the standardized reporting of company insights in the discipline of accounting (Qasim & Kharbat, 2020).

- **Regulatory compliance:** AI-powered systems play an important role in easing accounting procedures and guaranteeing compliance through adeptly checking records for conformity to norms and regulations and alerting situations of noncompliance or concerns (Otumo & Uwah, 2022). However, artificial intelligence (AI) can examine receipts and costs to discover any infractions of accounting policies and processes (Gusai, 2019).

- **Job Insecurity:** There is an increasing possibility that AI will reduce the demand of many accountants (Bako & Tanko, 2022) because the integration of AI into the accounting profession will force current accounting professionals to increase their technological skills because the need for unskilled new accountants will be reduced (Boritz & Stratopoulos, 2023). Akinadewo (2021) suggested that accountants undertake additional education and training to learn a variety of AI technologies and accounting software packages to improve their functional skills, efficacy, and productivity.

2.4. Role of accountants in an AI-based accounting environment

Like in most sectors, disruptive technologies are also grabbing accounting fields with their monumental blessing. This blessing can turn into a curse if accounting professionals are not able to cope with the blistering pace of disruptive AI technologies. The skills and competencies of accountants must be updated to address the changing environment (Moll & Yigitbasioğlu, 2019). Arntz et al. (2017) state that, regardless of the workload variety between workplaces within this sector, bookkeeping, accounting, and auditing are likely to be automated in the coming years. This, in turn, calls for, in reaction to automation, accountants may specialize in financial analysis, strategic advice, or system improvement.

The ever-evolving environment of daily disclosure, digitalization in business and learning, the adoption of digital wallets and online accounting, outsourcing, and changing consumer preferences are transforming the accounting profession, necessitating the acquisition of new skills, especially in engineering, and ushering in an entirely new type of accounting professional (Gulin et al., 2019). Accountants must learn new skills to adapt to developing technology, ensuring that they can

assess automated outcomes, manage risks, and contribute to educated, data-driven decisions for businesses in the context of AI integration. Professionals confronted with a major change toward technological advancement must adapt quickly to thrive both professionally and materially since failure in doing so can cause issues in maintaining their current positions as well as competing with peers who have adopted the move (Aljazeera & Al-Sartawi, 2023).

However, many believe that AI can be used as a primary tool for decision-making. However, according to Agrawal et al. (2019) artificial intelligence can directly substitute investment for manpower in the case of prediction tasks and may implicitly impact decision tasks by increasing or reducing the corresponding returns to labor versus investment for decision functions. This ultimately means that the task of decision-making cannot be completely replaced by AI because Chui et al. (2016) state that AI is currently suitable for predictable physical work, data processing, and data collection; however, for unpredictable physical work, stakeholder interaction, the application of expertise, and the management of other AI methods lack skills, as it cannot replace human feelings and environmental considerations, which are the key aspects of decision-making. However, when dealing with uncertainty and ambiguity in corporate decision-making, people can still provide a more comprehensive, intuitive approach (Jarrahi, 2018). As a result, different scholars emphasize a human-AI integrated decision-making environment that can compensate for each other's shortcomings effectively (Huang & Rust, 2018; Shrestha et al., 2019). Accountants may use AI to quickly evaluate large amounts of financial data, derive useful insights, and make immediate, data-driven guidance to improve decision-making processes. However, Leitner-Hanetseder et al. (2021) state that humans will need to employ digital innovations wisely and, to a certain extent, cooperate with artificial intelligence (AI) technology.

As machines take over conventional accounting chores, accountants must focus on data analysis and learning, and academia should educate essential technological competencies for Industry 4.0, collaborate with businesses to satisfy market demands, and stress both the technical and interpersonal abilities of businesses (Mai, 2022). Professionals in accounting must accept change in their work environment and learn new skills for long-term advantages; at the same time, IT skills, business advice skills, and technology literacy are critical talents for accountants in today's world (Alfares & Şavli, 2023). Banța et al. (2022) state that accountants' abilities should be improved so that they can use these technologies effectively and continue to provide important services.

2.5. AI and ethics in accounting professions

Traditionally, accountants have relied on organizational ethics to demonstrate professional ethics (Jaijairam, 2017), but the advent of new technologies such as blockchain, big data, the Internet of Things (IoT), AI, and sophisticated software, along with different machine learning algorithms, has raised ethical concerns that need to be addressed (Fischer, 2022; Liu et al., 2019; Sherif & Mohsin, 2021). Because of the integration of AI, concerns have been raised regarding the possible negative effects of AI on society, including employment displacement, ethical quandaries in passing responsibility to computers, challenges of societal control, and algorithmic blunders (Makridakis, 2017), and this undoubtedly significantly affects the professional field of accounting (Stancheva-Todorova, 2018). Moll and Yigitbasioglu (2019) state the immediate need to examine the increasing accounting demands in the digital economy and identify the critical skills that accountants must learn to remain relevant and valuable because the application and development of artificial intelligence are fraught with ethical and legal quandaries in the accounting and auditing fields (Jauhainen & Lehner, 2022). On the other hand, according to Vărzaru (2022) AI addresses certain ethical difficulties in managerial accounting and adds new ethical challenges, implying that, despite professional concerns, AI will have a considerable influence on managerial accounting.

The study of Bonsón et al. (2021) reveals that a substantial portion of European listed companies are increasingly interested in artificial intelligence (AI), whereas ethical AI implementation is still in its early stages, with variances based on the company's size, industry, and geographical region, providing insights for both researchers and businesses. It is difficult to establish ethics for AI since it involves both top-down techniques, which incorporate ethical concepts and human perceptions, and bottom-up strategies, in which AI develops ethical conduct through incentives, which frequently necessitate a combination of both (Goh et al., 2019). According to Ucoglu (2020), the Big Four firms are growing their AI initiatives in the fields of accounting and auditing, which calls for regulatory and ethical monitoring to handle related privacy laws, security threats, and ethical issues. The increasing acceptance of artificial intelligence over the coming decade will have an impact on ecological, social, and administrative parameters, necessitating ethical and liable AI execution, with accountants expected to play a vital part due to their adherence to ethics and participation in legislation, managing data, and cross-functional groups (Stancheva-Todorova, 2022). To retain confidence in the accounting industry, it is critical to incorporate ethics into the formation and implementation of future technologies (Boulianne et al., 2023). The use of AI in auditing and accounting involves not only ethical problems related to conflicts of interest and ethical reasoning but also the critical task of ensuring that AI performs with uncompromising ethical integrity (Maharani et al., 2023).

AI technologies, such as machine learning and robotic process automation (RPA), have altered normal accounting operations, enabling more efficient and precise data processing (Sreseli, 2023). However, the incorporation of AI into accounting has led to serious ethical problems. According to Barišić (2022) AI-driven accounting judgments might lead to prejudice, discrimination, and a lack of transparency. These difficulties are exacerbated by the existing lack of accountability frameworks, which leaves it unclear who is accountable when AI systems fail. Despite these ethical issues, there is still a lack

of research discussing how governance frameworks might be adopted to handle the unique ethical difficulties associated with AI. Most previous studies focused on identifying ethical issues rather than providing solutions (Fülöp et al., 2023; Ashok et al., 2022). This paper fills that gap by presenting an applicable governance framework for AI in accounting.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Objective of the study

Research on AI implementation in accounting practices has increased over time. The integration and implementation of AI in the accounting profession results in the creation of some ethical problems that require solutions. It is argued that artificial intelligence ethics are critical (Fülöp et al., 2023). The next generation of competent accounting professionals will require not only traditional expertise but also understanding in the areas of IT, AI, and RPA, as well as strong social skills (Florentina & Madalina, 2021). The incorporation of technology necessitates ethical concerns, and social competencies play a role in negotiating the ethical implications of AI applications, supporting competent decision-making, and ensuring the ethical implementation of modern innovations in accounting processes.

In this study, the main objective is to identify the ethical problems created by AI implementation in accounting processes and develop an ethical governance framework to address those problems. A systematic review of the studies will help address all the problems to craft a comprehensive framework to be developed and followed to mitigate ethical risks.

3.2. Review procedure

The steps of the systematic literature review suggested by Kitchenham (2004) have been used by several authors worldwide (Stapić et al., 2012; Abedin, 2022) and also followed to conduct this study. To search the relevant literature, Web of Science, Scopus, ResearchGate, and Google Scholar were considered by following the authors (Kotenko et al., 2021; Sarker & Islam, 2022). The keywords given in Table 1 were used to identify the relevant literature:

Table 1 Keywords used for the literature search.

Artificial intelligence or AI	AND	Ethics	AND	Accounting
OR		OR		OR
Cognitive software/technology		Morality		Accounting profession
OR		OR		OR
Smart technology		Values		Auditing
OR				OR
Machine intelligence				Financial reporting
OR				OR
Automated reasoning				Accounting practice
OR				
Intelligent automation				
OR				
Machine learning (ML)				
OR				
Robotic intelligence				
OR				
Computerized intelligence				
OR				
Digital intelligence				

An extensive scrutinization of articles, abstracts, and keywords of articles published in the accounting and business field is performed to identify the relevant articles that were published between 2017 and 2023. As given in Figure 1, through this process, 3451 articles were selected, and only 15 articles were selected at the initial stage; the quality of the articles was analyzed on the basis of the overall presentation and the attainment of the research objectives. The inclusion and exclusion of papers are limited on the basis of this timeframe with an intention to grasp the most recent ethical phenomenon concerning AI implementation in accounting practices.

To avoid excluding key papers, a forward and backward search was introduced to find relevant articles as suggested by Wolfswinkel et al. (2013). As shown in Figure 1, the references of the articles were screened out (backward search) and ResearchGate search (forward search) to reduce the likelihood of exclusion of relevant articles. This, however, results in the identification of 4 more relevant articles, and ultimately, the total number of articles becomes 19. Data were gathered by examining the full text of each article.

Figure 1 Process of systematic literature review.

3.3. Contextual data

Approximately 36.84% of the selected papers were published in 2023, 15.79% in 2022, 10.53% in 2021, 21.05% in 2020, and 5.26% each during 2019, 2018, and 2017. This highlights the considerable interest in determining the ethical landscape of AI implementation in accounting practices. The screening process depicted in Figure 1 was performed independently by the authors to avoid potential biases. To examine the reliability of the selection process, Cohen’s kappa was calculated. The screening procedure of the articles produces a Cohen’s kappa value of 0.49, which is regarded as acceptable according to (McHugh, 2012). This illustrates the accuracy and stability of the selection process to ensure the validity, reliability, and credibility of findings for making a significant contribution to accounting research.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Existing studies

Table 2 provides a detailed summary of the extant research aimed at identifying ethical concerns for the integration of AI into the accounting profession. These works have been meticulously scrutinized and chosen on the basis of their extensive assessment of ethical quandaries resulting from AI usage in accounting. By rigorously examining and synthesizing the findings from these selected publications, this research hopes to shed light on the ethical environment surrounding the incorporation of artificial intelligence in the accounting industry.

4.2. Ethical challenges related to AI adoption in accounting professions

Table 3 contains information about the ethical issues that arise as a result of AI integration in the accounting profession, emphasizing the complicated challenges that come with maintaining ethical standards in the context of technological development.

4.2.1. Accountability

Zhang et al. (2023) reported significant ethical problems concerning accountability in AI creation and integration into management accounting. The primary focus in the creation of AI was on judicious technology selection and the need for developer credentials to prevent overconfidence in new algorithms. When using AI, makers, client companies, management accountants, and legislators must collaborate to achieve accurate and beneficial results. However, according to Lehner et al. (2022) ethical problems associated with accountability while integrating AI into accounting are important concerns. Their study suggests that there are issues with incomprehensible algorithms and underscores the importance of holding corporations accountable for accurate data usage; consequently, difficulties in describing complicated AI systems are noted, prompting external examination for accountability. Moreover, the significance of ethical algorithmic accountability and its influence on decision-making models is also seen as critical. However, the use of augmented or autonomous AI in auditing is considered to incorporate risk into the accountability of the profession and raises the following question: 'Is it possible to establish accountability systems for complicated technologies and distribute responsibilities?' (Munoko et al., 2020). Yoon (2020) focused on three essential areas for assessing the influence of modern technology on accounting ethics: decision-making, accountability, and ethics education. Concerning accountability, the discussion centers on the 'responsibility gap', which emphasizes the difficulty of assigning blame to artificial entities that learn and function autonomously. If people delegate duties to machines, it creates a dilemma.

Table 2 Ethical challenges of AI adoption.

Studies	Main Focus of Studies	Ethical Challenges
(Zhang et al., 2023)	Investigating the ethical implications of AI in management accounting and offering guidelines to lessen potential hazards.	Security & Privacy. Misuse of Data. Accountability. Accessibility. Transparency. Trust. Bias.
(Fülöp et al., 2023)	The primary goal is to investigate the ethical issues and consequences of utilizing artificial intelligence in accounting businesses, with a focus on the need for regulatory supervision in developing ethical rules for AI in the area.	Lack of Ethical Principles. Bias. Discrimination.
(Beerbaum, 2023)	This research aims to conduct a detailed review of the literature to examine the possible influence of blockchain technology on the discipline of accounting, with a specific emphasis on the effect of AI-enhanced auditing methodologies.	Security & Privacy. Intellectual Property Rights. Bias. Misuse of Technology.
(Marques et al., 2023)	The primary goal is to investigate how the convergence of AI, Big Data, and the Internet of Things (IoT) might affect and improve the management accounting profession by increasing work efficiency and merging human and intelligence system competencies.	Bias. Accessibility.
(Latifah et al., 2023)	This study aims to investigate the evolution of ethical conduct in Artificial Intelligence (AI) by studying potential accountants' conformity with their personal and corporate principles.	Bias. Security & Privacy. Data Transparency. Discrimination.
(Daoud, 2023)	The purpose of this study is to analyze the ethical influence of technical breakthroughs (blockchain, AI, neural networks) on the accounting profession, with a focus on the need for strong ethical frameworks and rules to ensure responsible and ethical behavior in the digitized accounting profession.	Security & Privacy. Responsible Data Use. Employment Issue. Bias.
(Peng et al., 2023)	This article examines the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in the accounting profession, including financial reporting, the auditing process, and decision-making, to enhance effectiveness, precision, and support for decisions.	Employment Issue. Security & Privacy. Bias.
(Lehner et al., 2022)	This research seeks to determine and examine the ethical issues of employing AI-based systems of accounting for making decisions.	Objectivity. Security & Privacy. Transparency. Accountability. Trust.
(Hasan, 2022)	The primary goal of this article is to analyze the transformative influence of AI on the accounting and auditing professions, highlighting the importance of multidisciplinary collaboration and readiness for Industry 4.0 issues.	Financial Fraud. Bias. Employment Issues.
(Vărzaru, 2022)	The main aim is to explore these ethical concerns concerning accountants' perceptions of the utility, efficiency, and efficacy of integrating artificial intelligence in management accounting.	Security & Privacy. Transparency. Trust.
(Losbichler & Lehner, 2021)	The authors aim to investigate AI's limits for handling complicated structures and sketch out the possibilities for human-machine engagement in information handling.	Unethical Decision Making. Lack of Control. Bias.

(Sherif & Mohsin, 2021)	To determine how merging blockchain, IoT, and AI technology will stop fraud in accounting and ethical myopia.	Bias. Objectivity.
(Munoko et al., 2020)	Utilizing prior research and deductions based on the reported usage of AI by auditing companies, to present a conceptual study of the practical ethical and societal challenges surrounding AI in auditing.	Accountability. Accessibility. Autonomy of Users. Security & Privacy. Bias. Transparency. Beneficence. Employment Issues.
(Gunz & Thorne, 2020)	The research aims to bridge the gap between technical and ethical aspects of accounting decision-making, especially in the context of advancing technology.	Financial Fraud. Unethical Decision Making.
(Yoon, 2020)	Focuses on the advantages of technological advances in accounting, particularly artificial intelligence, big data analysis, and blockchain.	Security & Privacy. Technology Driven Judgment. Lack of Accountability.
(Chukwuani & Egiyi, 2020)	The primary goal of this research is to examine the impact of artificial intelligence on the field of accounting, evaluate the level of automation in accounting procedures, and explore how twenty-first-century accounting professionals may embrace the improvements of new developments.	Financial Fraud. Security & Privacy.
(Zemánková, 2019)	The primary goal is to evaluate how artificial intelligence and blockchain are changing audit and the accounting profession, with an emphasis on products from prominent consulting companies.	Financial Fraud. Bias. Unethical Decision Making.
(Sutton et al., 2018)	This debate dives into the influence of systems based on knowledge on user memory and comprehension, arguing for a research strategy that stresses information transfer during job activities to preserve human skill and its relevance in business decision-making.	Security & Privacy. Information Validity.
(Kokina & Davenport, 2017)	Focuses on investigating the influence of artificial intelligence on accounting and auditing, including its existing capabilities, industry examples, potential biases, and future research implications.	Objectivity. Employment Issues. Bias.

4.2.2. Accessibility

Accessibility has become a key ethical concern (Zhang et al., 2023). The majority of survey participants were concerned about AI's lack of accessibility, citing problems such as user unfriendliness, inability to adapt to changes in accounting practices, and lack of legislative access. The study emphasized the adverse effects of inaccessible artificial intelligence (AI) on human autonomy, which blocks management accountants' ability to appropriately manage AI systems. Simultaneously, Marques et al. (2023) suggest that access to skewed and misleading data from AI systems can lead to ethical difficulties. On the other hand, a question was raised regarding "Could the innovation be developed in a manner that makes it accessible and simple to apply for numerous individuals?" (Munoko et al., 2020). The study examined AI aspects (intelligence, data, computational complexity, and retrieval) by employing Wright's ethical checklist to identify possible dangers to principles related to transparency and accessibility, which were substantiated by references to pertinent studies.

4.2.3. Autonomy of users

The possibility of excessive influence on inexperienced users who might not know how to interact with the system appropriately is an ethical issue with respect to user autonomy in AI (Munoko et al., 2020). However, it is argued that current data protection regulations fall short of adequately addressing the special risks associated with predictive analytics. The ethical implications also highlight the importance of taking proactive steps to provide users with the information and skills required to operate AI systems autonomously. Achieving a balance between system guidance and user autonomy is crucial for avoiding accidentally disclosing sensitive information while explaining procedures.

Table 3 Ethical challenges associated with AI adoption in accounting professions.

Ethical Challenges	Supporting Studies
Accountability	(Zhang et al., 2023; Lehner et al., 2022; Munoko et al., 2020; Yoon, 2020).
Accessibility	(Zhang et al., 2023; Marques et al., 2023; Munoko et al., 2020).
Autonomy of users.	(Munoko et al., 2020).
Bias	(Zhang et al., 2023; Beerbaum, 2023; Fülöp et al., 2023; Latifah et al., 2023; Daoud, 2023; Marques et al., 2023; Peng et al., 2023; Hasan, 2022; Losbichler & Lehner, 2021; Sherif & Mohsin, 2021; Munoko et al., 2020; Zemánková, 2019; Kokina & Davenport, 2017).
Beneficence	(Munoko et al., 2020).
Confidentiality	(Daoud, 2023).
Discrimination	(Latifah et al., 2023; Fülöp et al., 2023)
Employment issues	(Daoud, 2023; Peng et al., 2023; Hasan, 2022; Munoko et al., 2020; Kokina & Davenport, 2017).
Financial fraud	(Hasan, 2022; Chukwuani & Egiji, 2020; Gunz & Thorne, 2020; Zemánková, 2019).
Information validity	(Sutton et al., 2018).
Intellectual property rights	(Beerbaum, 2023).
Lack of ethical principles	(Fülöp et al., 2023).
Lack of control	(Losbichler & Lehner, 2021).
Misuse of data & technology	(Zhang et al., 2023; Beerbaum, 2023).
Objectivity	(Lehner et al., 2022; Sherif & Mohsin, 2021; Kokina & Davenport, 2017).
Responsible data use	(Daoud, 2023).
Security & privacy	(Zhang et al., 2023; Beerbaum, 2023; Latifah et al., 2023; Peng et al., 2023; Lehner et al., 2022; Vărzaru, 2022; Munoko et al., 2020; Yoon, 2020; Chukwuani & Egiji, 2020; Sutton et al., 2018).
Transparency	(Zhang et al., 2023; Latifah et al., 2023; Daoud, 2023; Lehner et al., 2022; Vărzaru, 2022; Munoko et al., 2020; Kokina & Davenport, 2017).
Trust	(Zhang et al., 2023; Lehner et al., 2022; Vărzaru, 2022).
Technology driven judgment	(Yoon, 2020).
Unethical decision making	(Losbichler & Lehner, 2021; Gunz & Thorne, 2020; Zemánková, 2019).

4.2.4. Bias

AI systems that often depend on rule-based algorithms based on expert judgment and knowledge may accidentally transmit human bias while making decisions due to knowledge constraints, personal emotions, and other external factors (Zhang et al., 2023). The overreliance on generating artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms on particular kinds of data or input creates the possibility of bias in the created material (Beerbaum, 2023), offering an ethical risk that should be carefully considered before these kinds of technologies are used. Sherif and Mohsin (2021) also stated that biased algorithms are a considerable issue. Fülöp et al. (2023) argue that artificial intelligence (AI) may raise certain ethical concerns since it can gain knowledge on its own via unique algorithms and input data. AI ethics comprises ethical complications in AI creation and development, particularly confronting concerns of human bias in data, data security, and openness; an ongoing obstacle is confronting inappropriate historical biases in the data gathered by AI systems (Latifah et al., 2023). A major problem is that the data utilized by these technologies for learning are frequently biased, leading to occasions where AI systems have evolved discriminatory tendencies, including ethnic prejudice or bias based on other variables (Marques et al., 2023). However, depending on automated technologies in accounting raises concerns regarding algorithmic bias and credibility, as judgments frequently rely on complex algorithms that may lack transparency and equity (Daoud, 2023). Peng et al. (2023) also stated that biases are a source of ethical problems, but they do not even clarify any specific kind of bias that is dominant in the accounting industry because of the incorporation of AI in accounting tasks. Moreover, the possibility of bias in automatic decision-making procedures is a major concern, prompting accounting specialists to be diligent in finding and correcting biases in algorithms, training data, and automated process design. Hasan (2022) noted that AI applications have the potential to have algorithms that are predatory, deceitful, internally biased, or incorporate human logic mistakes or human biases. However, AI can learn from human bias because AI has no self-interest, which can work as a major driving force of ethical problems (Losbichler & Lehner, 2021). The use of auditor-labeled data in the setting of AI may perpetuate or magnify preexisting human biases (Munoko et al., 2020). This finding indicates that artificial intelligence systems may learn and replicate biases contained within the labeled data given by auditors. Moreover, there is a risk of economic and reputational damage when decisions regarding investments, influenced by biased algorithms, diverge from the fundamental audit and accounting principle of ensuring reliable

and equitable financial statements (Zemánková, 2019). Furthermore, Kokina and Davenport (2017) raised issues regarding data-driven bias, bias through interaction, emergent bias, and conflicting-goals bias while dealing with AI.

4.2.5. Beneficence

According to Munoko et al. (2020), in the realm of automated AI in the fields of accounting and auditing, ethical concerns concerning beneficence include the prospect of job losses, particularly in back-office tasks, resulting in the formation of an "invisible workforce". This move may influence the accounting profession by raising issues about recruitment methods that may impact the number of students majoring in accounting. As AI becomes more widely used, professionals may find it more difficult to schedule, report, and invoice. The auditing profession may be perceived as too commercialized by the public as a result of greater usage of artificial intelligence (AI), which may exacerbate client-auditor disagreements. *"Does the endeavour serve broader community objectives as well as values, or merely the goals of the data collector?"*

4.2.6. Confidentiality

Confidentiality is a fundamental ethical problem because it provides trust, privacy, and safeguarding of crucial information, hence preserving the dignity of professional relations. Daoud (2023) noted ethical concerns regarding the confidentiality of customer information and highlighted that maintaining the confidentiality of customer information, protecting sensitive data, and using information only for legitimate purposes are fundamental ethical requirements that accountants must follow.

4.2.7. Discrimination

There is an important ethical issue related to discrimination that ultimately results from a lack of transparency and other historical biases (Latifah et al., 2023). This, however, is closely related to another ethical concern of fairness and equity. The ethical issues regarding fairness and equity come from discrimination, bias, and societal disgrace. Fülöp et al. (2023) address problems related to moral issues of discrimination that lead to two alarming questions: *"Are we all identical? Can robotics operate without professional reasoning?"*. Answering these questions can yield a substantial understanding of human competence and the use of AI in workplace decision-making.

4.2.8. Employment Issues

The adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) in the accounting profession raises ethical quandaries for businesses because there is a possibility of enormous job displacement (Daoud, 2023). As a result, maintaining the public's trust and upholding the standards of the accounting profession become crucial concerns. However, artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming the accounting profession in a variety of ways, including task automation, fraud detection, forecasting, and specialization. Making good financial decisions requires a combination of AI-generated data and human skill (Peng et al., 2023). It is also evident that automating certain routine tasks raises serious ethical considerations, as there is a risk of potential job loss. Hasan (2022) used a term called 'technological unemployment' to highlight the impact of AI in the accounting profession. According to previous studies, artificial intelligence dramatically alters the employment model of the accounting industry. This, in turn, may disturb society's harmony by increasing crime rates, which are closely associated with human survival at the expense of ethical and moral considerations. The ethical impact on the job because of the use of AI was also identified by Munoko et al. (2020). According to the author, augmented AI can replace the traditional human role that can create an invisible workplace. The incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) in accounting poses ethical issues regarding shifting skill requirements, which might lead to reduced entry-level professions (Kokina & Davenport, 2017). Although senior accounting professionals expect human functions to continue, the transition to AI may result in a gradual loss of jobs, with remaining roles emphasizing cooperation with automated systems and tasks asking for deep client comprehension, posing difficulties for entry-level recruits seeking experience.

4.2.9. Financial fraud

The application of AI in the auditing and accounting professions creates ethical concerns, such as the evolving nature of fraud when new forms of illegal conduct arise (Hasan, 2022). As financial crime has increased and AI has been employed more often in recent decades, there is growing concern about the prerequisites for effective strategies to address and mitigate these shifting challenges. According to Chukwuani and Egiyi (2020), artificial intelligence has been integrated into accounting systems to improve security by monitoring digital footprints. Nevertheless, human monitoring is still needed since financial fraud is a challenging issue to eliminate fully. Fraudulent reporting via modern technology is connected to a weakened social interface, which reduces ethical issues in reporting (Gunz & Thorne, 2020). It is further posited that taxpayers are more likely to engage in fraudulent disclosure when prosocial ideals collide with their principles than when values coincide or when the platform emphasizes economic rewards. The study also shows that taxpayers' remorse about falsifying mediates the relationship between value-incongruent prosocial sharing and tax reporting integrity, which is consistent with the idea of moral

authorization. Additionally, despite the aim of democratizing financial advice, there is a danger of regional disputes and financial marginalization, challenges to financial safety owing to complicated relationships, and probable polarization of communities (Zemánková, 2019).

4.2.10. Information validity

Artificial intelligence (AI) in accounting can have an ethical impact on information validity by offering a risk of biased algorithms and autonomous decision-making, creating problems with the accuracy and fairness of financial information.

Data collection and potential abuse, particularly in light of recent scandals, emphasize the ethical quandary of information validity in AI-driven accounting and the importance of instilling ethical principles into autonomous machines (Sutton et al., 2018). This is consistent with current discussions about AI and ethics, which highlight the role of robotics, machine learning (ML), and data privacy in preserving moral norms.

4.2.11. Intellectual property rights

Intellectual property rights (IPRs) create an array of tough ethical challenges that differ depending on one's position. These rights are aimed at encouraging innovative and creative thinking by offering creative people the opportunity to profit financially from their work. Generative AI poses ethical concerns about confidentiality and intellectual property rights violations, and it also contributes to the creation of deep fakes with malicious intent and potential bias. When technology is abused, human effort and intellectual ability may be displaced (Beerbaum, 2023).

4.2.12. Lack of ethical principles

An important issue is the ethical principles of artificial intelligence (AI) (Fülöp et al., 2023). The authors addressed an important question: *“What are the ethical principles you apply in your work, and what do you think should be the ones applied by AI?”* It is also suggested that the decision-making capabilities of sophisticated technologies cannot be matched with human consciousness and that artificial intelligence lacks different steps of ethics, responsibility, and existence, which are closely related to human consciousness, which is developed with the help of different qualifications and intensities and through the human development stage and social influence.

4.2.13. Lack of control

Effective artificial intelligence adoption in the accounting sector requires striking a balance between ethical concerns and efficiency gains. Lack of control in accounting is an ethical problem that results from AI limitations, such as managing complexity, challenges in recognizing and controlling complex procedures, and biases in the processing of data through machines (Losbichler & Lehner, 2021). Nevertheless, the growing complexity of corporate management, driven by globalization and fast digitalization, presents problems for cybernetics. However, invisible factors and system dynamics make perfect forecasts difficult, stressing the importance of patterns. According to the authors' interpretation, managers have limited management choices due to the interconnectivity of aspects. While AI can improve control, the inherent complications highlight the impossibility of making exact projections, posing ethical questions about accounting decisions.

4.2.14. Misuse of data and technology

In the research of Zhang et al. (2023), respondents stated substantial concerns regarding data exploitation, with conglomerate businesses being especially anxious about the possible misuse of data when integrating internal and external data between headquarters and affiliates. Even so, the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) technology being misused, resulting in the violation of intellectual property rights, is an important issue (Beerbaum, 2023). Serious concern has been expressed about the potential use of generative AI to create deceptive audiovisual content, such as phoney movies or images, with the risk of negative consequences such as political interference and misinformation propagation (Beerbaum, 2023).

4.2.15. Objectivity

The study by Lehner et al. (2022) focuses on the ethical issues of employing artificial intelligence to achieve impartiality in the process of making decisions, emphasizing examples including bias in networking sites, loan and audit ratings, and audit procedures. Nevertheless, it is clear that the issue of objectivity largely impacts moral judgment and moral excitement, as both would be incorrect owing to the presence of biased information or algorithms. Kokina and Davenport (2017) also draw attention to the dearth of objectivity and issue a warning, pointing out that when intelligent computers are used, their creations or interactions with people often reflect their biases. The use of AI (machine learning, prediction forecasting, assistive intelligence, augmenting intelligence, autonomous intelligence) in accounting fields raises an important question (Sherif & Mohsin, 2021): *“Will the exclusion of accountants from certain tasks because of the use of AI require retraining accountants to focus more on auditing AI software to validate its objectivity?”*

4.2.16. Responsible data use

As noted by Daoud (2023), the ethical problem of using AI in the accounting profession is the proper application of technologies such as blockchain and AI. Even if these technologies increase efficiency, it is vital to manage consumer data correctly. As a result, accountants must adhere to data privacy rules, describe the reasons for collecting data, and obtain express consent from their customers. Client confidentiality and the use of data only for appropriate purposes are two important issues that need to be safeguarded.

4.2.17. Security and privacy

Data privacy and security are important for the ability of AI-based accounting to safeguard sensitive financial data, ensure regulatory compliance, and maintain confidentiality, trust, and integrity in financial transactions. Ignoring these aspects and not giving them importance may lead to unauthorized entry, data breaches, and other issues. This, however, has received the attention of several authors. Zhang et al. (2023), after conducting 47 interviews with different institutions, reported that data privacy and security are the alarming ethical risks associated with the development and use of artificial intelligence (AI) in managerial accounting. Nonetheless, many recent studies have provided strong support for this claim since they show similar points of view. Therefore, considering the ethical and legal implications of generative AI in accounting is essential, particularly in light of concerns about data security, privacy, and potential biases (Beerbaum, 2023). Latifah et al. (2023) argue, however, that substantial challenges accompany technical advancements. These challenges include inaccurate data, security and privacy, and other ethical issues related to AI-based technology, all of which affect users, programmers, and the community as a whole. However, automation is making data security and privacy in the accounting sector an alarming concern (Daoud, 2023). Despite the many benefits of artificial intelligence in accounting. Peng et al. (2023) state that unresolved issues with data security, human control, and ethics must be addressed to ensure ethical and successful use. As reliance on artificial intelligence grows, safeguarding financial data from accidental access becomes increasingly important. Therefore, it is essential to safeguard sensitive financial data against cyberattacks and illegal access as technological innovation becomes more widely used. Loss of data privacy is also regarded by other authors (Yoon, 2020). A thematic coding carried out by Lehner et al. (2022) also stated that privacy is a major ethical challenge in AI-based decision-making in accounting. Ethical considerations such as security, transparency, and trust, as well as additional difficulties such as anonymity, responsibility, privacy, reliability, and data protection, have been identified as impediments to the deployment of AI solutions in management accounting (Vărzaru, 2022). Zhang et al. (2023) noted that developers must follow technological standards, laws, and ethical rules to provide unbiased, dependable systems with minimum analysis, no data reuse, priority data protection and privacy, and require technical instructions for users. Proper security and safety of the system are needed with proper protection and support through strong cyberdefence (Chukwuani & Egiyi, 2020). Moreover, the use of AI in the auditing profession has raised concerns regarding obtaining quality data and data of different formats, which are believed to put the values of data privacy and security at utmost risk (Munoko et al., 2020). To unearth the ethical issues surrounding AI, it is evident that information privacy is a matter of controversial issue (Sutton et al., 2018).

4.2.18. Transparency

The nature of artificial intelligence has led to serious concerns about its transparency and use (Zhang et al., 2023). According to their study, different stakeholders stress the need to resolve transparency problems by focusing on the risks connected with making management decisions on the basis of AI-generated content. The need for artificial intelligence (AI) systems to explain their technical operations, ensure interpretable reasoning and support decision-making with relevant arguments highlights the ethical issues of transparency in the use of AI in the accounting profession (Latifah et al., 2023). Nonetheless, Daoud (2023) states that the increasing use of artificial intelligence (AI) in accounting raises ethical questions regarding transparency, which require measures including periodic audits to handle bias concerns and encouraging accountants to emphasize transparency and equitable consideration for clients and stakeholders in digital spaces while weighing the more extensive ethical repercussions of digitization. The ethical problem of transparency in artificial intelligence (AI) decisions is complicated, with concerns arising from an incomplete understanding of its nature and extent (Lehner et al., 2022). This study raises questions about data availability, computational opacity, and the private, black-box aspect of neural systems. Identifying biases when there is a lack of transparency, which is crucial for traceability and auditability and requires ongoing monitoring, is challenging. Although complete transparency is required in some situations (e.g., corporate social responsibility), it is not always feasible or desirable, as it may cause a violation of privacy or reveal the trade secrets of business entities. Moreover, the possibility of manipulation and its influence on algorithmic decisions underscore the complex connection between accountability, ethical conscience, and transparency. The ethical concerns around transparency are further supported by the findings of Vărzaru's (2022) study, which indicates that customers' perceptions of the use of AI in management accounting are influenced primarily by three ethical factors: transparency, safety, and trustworthiness. In the auditing profession, ethical risks are raised around the transparency of information because unexplainable AI hampers the understandability of auditors (Munoko et al., 2020). The opacity of sophisticated AI technologies, for example, machine

learning and deep learning neural networks, undermines transparency in accounting decisions, demanding the study of viable remedies (Kokina & Davenport, 2017).

4.2.19. Trust

There are extensive doubts about the efficacy and trustworthiness of artificially intelligent systems in managerial accounting, citing the potential difficulties conceptual AI models might experience in assessing genuine data and addressing real-world issues and emphasizing the inherent hazards of relying entirely on AI-generated results (Zhang et al., 2023). Trust and trustworthiness in artificial intelligence-driven accounting are multilayered, spanning individual, firm, and organizational levels, with an indispensable fourth level impacted through technology design; difficulties result from the requirement for perceived trustworthiness, which extends beyond AI's indicated functions to ensure proper alignment with human priorities (Lehner et al., 2022). The research emphasizes trust concerns related to algorithmic biases, such as responsibility, transparency, and accountability, underlining their critical role in human–AI connections and as accelerators for moral conduct in the complex terrain of ethical decisions in accounting. However, Vărzaru (2022) cites trust as a critical ethical factor that influences users' opinions of AI in management accounting. Furthermore, trust emerges as a critical ethical factor that positively affects AI usability and performance in management accounting, emphasizing the importance of these components in shaping user perceptions. In particular, the study suggests that ethical issues related to AI adoption can be regarded as opportunities to build confidence in AI solutions rather than as impediments.

4.2.20. Technology-driven judgment

The introduction of AI into accounting opens a wide range of opportunities, but it also raises several ethical questions. Ethical difficulties occur in technologically driven judgments, highlighting human accountability for outcomes since robots cannot make ethical decisions on their own (Yoon, 2020). Additionally, society demands human engagement for ethical accounting judgments, notably in decision-making, accountability, and teaching, because robots are morally neutral and lack comprehension of genuine social behavior.

4.2.21. Unethical decision-making

The ethical challenges in AI-powered accounting choices include addressing social voices, assessing cultural norms, and switching to rule-based implementation. Other ethical issues include worries about biased sampling and the potential decline in partiality and irrational managerial behavior (Losbichler & Lehner, 2021).

Concurrently, Gunz and Thorne (2020) state that humans tend to act differently from computers and other humans. Humans tend to lie before technologies that hamper the decision-making capabilities of developed software, which can lead to unethical decisions. However, as stated by the authors, ethical issues in AI decision-making stem from the intricate nature of adaptation and learning, which goes beyond preprogrammed algorithms, challenges conventional expert judgment, and raises questions about unintended effects and accountability.

AI extensively depends on data and requires high-quality data to learn and influence human decisions (Zemánková, 2019). Biased or unfair outcomes may occur if data that are used to train artificial intelligence (AI) systems contain biases or are of poor quality. This may encourage unethical acts and behaviors by professionals. The reliance on the quality of data raises questions about justice, accountability, and the possible amplification of current biases in AI platforms.

5. Future Research Direction

This systematic analysis investigated the fundamental ethical issues raised by AI adoption in accounting, with a special emphasis on bias, privacy, responsibility, and trust. By combining data from significant research, it is obvious that the dynamic character of AI ethics needs a flexible yet effective governance system.

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in accounting practices creates numerous ethical challenges that require proactive solutions to ensure fair and responsible AI implementation. Most of the studies indicate several common key ethical concerns, such as security and privacy, bias, transparency, financial fraud, and accountability. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach that encompasses collaborative governance and work with proper education, ethical use of technology, ethical data use, a collaborative approach, increasing trust, improving cognitive skills, increasing human involvement, incorporating organizational and personal values, prioritizing transparency, accountability and fairness, policy formation, regulatory enforcement, strengthening cyber security, training, and technological innovation. Furthermore, the unemployment problem created by automation is a serious concern. To solve the unemployment problem, proper education and training are necessary. The lack of ethical principles in AI implementation and use calls for required standards from the appropriate authority. Additionally, issues regarding decision-making can be solved by following appropriate standards and guidelines. Above all, strong human involvement is necessary in the development and implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) in accounting practices. AI lacks the cognitive abilities that create biases. While developing algorithms, developers must

consider a neutral approach to avoid potential algorithmic biases. If algorithmic biases can be resolved during the development phase, the other consequent ethical problems can be mitigated automatically.

Intellectual property rights violations, a lack of control, a lack of accessibility, and objectivity are also noted as ethical problems related to AI implementation in the accounting profession. Determining direct solutions to these problems is not easy enough. However, an analysis of these studies suggests that technological innovations, legal and regulatory frameworks, ethical guidelines and education, and proper collaboration can be the best solutions. It is not possible to solve the ethical problems associated with AI integration in the accounting profession at one time because of the dynamic nature of artificial intelligence (AI). Additionally, defining what is right and what is wrong in an AI-integrated environment is difficult. Therefore, a dynamic approach must be considered at the organizational and enforcement levels. Figure 2 illustrates a comprehensive ethical governance framework that can be considered to solve the major ethical issues identified in the study:

The proposed governance framework outlined in this paper makes several contributions:

Artificial intelligence systems must be constantly checked to avoid algorithmic bias, which can perpetuate prejudice in financial decision-making. Organizations may verify that AI performs fairly well by implementing audit trials and conducting frequent system assessments. One of the key concerns about AI adoption is the "responsibility gap." This paradigm advocates for explicit lines of responsibility between AI developers, accountants, and regulatory organizations to guarantee that errors or biases can be tracked back to specific persons or systems. AI systems are advised to use explainable AI approaches to make decision-making processes visible and intelligible to human auditors and stakeholders.

Future research should delve deeper into the root causes of ethical problems regarding AI implementation and use in accounting practices to mitigate its impact effectively. However, integrated research can result in a more advanced ethical governance framework that can contribute to mitigating the dynamic ethical problems of AI use in the accounting profession. Research approaches that focus on particular ethical problems can also provide more advanced solutions. However, by adopting a multidisciplinary approach that combines insights from accounting, computer science, ethics, and organizational behavior, researchers can advance the understanding of the ethical implications of AI adoption and enhance the development of evidence-based practices for ethical governance in the digital era.

6. Implications for Theory and Practices

6.1. Theoretical implications

This study determines the ethical problems associated with artificial intelligence (AI) adoption in accounting practices. It does not identify any universal solutions to ethical problems. The nature of ethical dilemmas varies with the continuous upgradation of the AI system and depends on personal and situational characteristics.

The presented ethical governance framework in the study includes the most alarming problems and their methods of mitigation. This framework requires a collaborative approach from individuals, organisations, and concerned authorities. This can be further expanded by determining the roles and responsibilities of the concerned parties at every stage.

The findings of this study suggest a desire to develop and evaluate AI systems in the field of accounting with more advanced conceptual frameworks that consider ethical concerns. Scholars may contribute to the development of conceptual models that focus on links between technological progress, ethical decision making and organisational behavior to identify ethical features associated with the adoption of artificial intelligence. In addition, theoretical frameworks can help explain the social science processes that could affect the adoption of artificial intelligence and its ethics in a variety of organizational circumstances.

6.2. Practical implications

From a practical point of view, this research highlights the desire for organizations to have strong ethical governance frameworks in place when adopting artificial intelligence (AI). The suggested framework has important consequences for accounting professionals and companies. Accountants, for example, can protect their reputations from the negative effects of unethical AI use by incorporating ethical AI practices into corporate rules and practices. Furthermore, regulatory bodies should establish governance frameworks that protect data privacy, fairness, and accountability. As a result, a concerted effort by many stakeholders, each with their own set of duties and responsibilities, is required to assure the ethical use of AI and reduce the ethical hazards associated with algorithmic decision making. For example, employees should be trained on ethical guidelines, compliance and best practices to address and make ethical decisions. Moreover, management must put in place proper guidelines, provide training programs and establish channels of communication to respond to concerns. Finally, the organization as a whole needs to establish and enforce ethical governance frameworks, such as policies, procedures and accountability structures.

Figure 2 Ethical governance framework.

However, regulators and standard-setting bodies are critical in setting guidelines and ensuring compliance with ethical standards. AI developers play an important role in embedding ethical principles into the design and execution of AI algorithms. In addition, effective implementation strategies include the inclusion of ethical principles in policies, providing comprehensive training programs, setting up accountability frameworks, working with regulatory authorities and continuously evaluating and improving governance processes. Additionally, businesses can foster a culture of responsible use of artificial intelligence while ensuring that ethical issues are adequately addressed in their accounting practices by adopting these duties and using effective implementation methods.

7. Conclusion and Limitations

Artificial intelligence (AI) has changed significantly over the years because of recent developments and increased focus on implementing and using artificial intelligence in various sectors. In the accounting domain, AI has been used in recent years. Owing to the increase in the volume of use of AI in accounting practices, the number of related ethical dilemmas is also increasing.

The ethical issues surrounding the use of artificial intelligence in the accounting profession are reviewed in detail in this study, and a governance framework is suggested to address these issues. To reduce risks such as prejudice, privacy violations, and job displacement, the framework places a strong emphasis on the necessity of responsibility, openness, and ethical data usage. This paper emphasizes the importance of ethical governance in ensuring responsible AI deployment in the accounting profession by adding to both scholarly and practical discussions.

The use of AI in accounting practices has been increasing over the years, and ensuring ethical handling has become an alarming concern. On the basis of these problems, an ethical governance framework is suggested that incorporates regulatory compliance, ethical education and training, collaborative governance, technological innovation, transparency and accountability, and human-centered design to mitigate ethical risk by integrating different dimensions of the problem. In conclusion, companies may implement the governance architecture presented in this study to guarantee that AI systems are reliable, moral, and effective.

However, this may not be considered the standard for mitigating ethical risk because of the dynamic nature of AI development. Nevertheless, AI is covering increasingly more fields of accounting practices. Therefore, the scope of the suggested ethical governance framework can be expanded further. Future studies should concentrate on evaluating these governance models' performance in practical contexts and improving them to handle new ethical issues in AI. Existing and potential professionals in the accounting field must have diverse AI knowledge and skills to address present and upcoming ethical issues. AI cannot be a full replacement for humans. As a result, instead of fearing the loss of a job, obtaining the knowledge and skills to handle it is necessary to cope with advanced developments and mitigate ethical risks.

This study is secondary research. As a result, the limitations of the reviewed articles are also included in this research. Additionally, the study covers the timeframe of 2017--2023, so the relevant articles published after the timeframe are not included in this review. The limitation also applies to the article search procedure because there is always a chance that some relevant articles may not be found in the search.

Ethical Considerations

Not applicable.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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